

IMAGE HERMENEUTICS: A REFLECTIVE APPROACH IN POSTMODERN DIDACTICS

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Abstract

The article explores the potential of image hermeneutics as an instrument of critical reflection and meaningful learning within the postmodern didactics of visual arts. The case study, conducted over a short period in a vocational high school, 9th grade, specialization in Cultural Heritage, aimed to develop students' visual interpretation competence through the reflective analysis of Raphael Sanzio's fresco The School of Athens. The research was based on the design of a qualitative educational investigation, combining the hermeneutic analysis of the

artwork with reflective tools such as interpretation journals and attitudinal questionnaires. Postmodern education emphasizes the plurality of interpretations and rejects the idea of a single truth, favoring processes of reflection and dialogue.

The results revealed that the hermeneutic process stimulates critical thinking, cultural empathy, and the students' ability to connect visual meanings to philosophical and cultural contexts.

Keywords: hermeneutics, fresco, reflective analysis, empathy, postmodern didactics, interpretation journal.

1. Introduction

In the context of postmodern didactics, an essential role belongs to image hermeneutics, which, through its diverse range of interpretive, dialogic, and reflective tools, offers educators an integrative approach to the cultural-artistic heritage. Vocational education of a theological type emphasizes an image that gains cultural, symbolic, spiritual, and epistemic valences, enabling students to decode, in a profound manner, the visual meanings of the artwork. In this way, the image becomes a privileged instrument of interpretation, knowledge, and identity formation.

Within theological high schools, where visual education exists in close symbiosis with the iconographic tradition, with the anthropological dimension of the image, and with sacred symbolism, there is a need for an interpretive methodology capable not only of going beyond simple description but also of operating as a deep encounter with the values of the work of art. Through an image hermeneutics, we are offered an interpretive-reflective approach that places emphasis on meaning, context, experience, and dialogue.

Postmodern didactics, through hermeneutics, offers students the chance to enter into a stimulating dialogue with the image, to glimpse multiple meanings, and to reflect on the relationship between culture, visual, and identity.

Raphael Sanzio's fresco *The School of Athens* provides an ideal opportunity for such an approach, because it is a synthesis of Renaissance cultural values with an inclination toward the dialogue between faith and reason, and it is also an example of a symbolic representation of knowledge. For ninth-grade students in a theological high school, interpreting this painting offers a pedagogical occasion of major significance through: the analysis of visual symbols, the understanding of the relationship between Christian tradition and ancient culture, and reflection on the role of the community in the educational process.

From the viewpoint of such an aesthetic understanding, any work of art is open, through its ability to generate new interpretations and diverse additions of meaning. We thus notice the aspect by which hermeneutics assumes as new research domains imagination, visual language, and the artistic image, the work of art itself.

We revisit Jean Burgos's (2003) idea that the work of art does not address only one facet of the human, but the whole person, with the entire ensemble of their capacities. According to the French author's conception, the artist's great desire lies in the fact that the work should establish communication between the artist and all other recipients, being created so that each might attain an understanding similar to the artist's. However, the true significance of the work of art consists in the attitude that the receiver develops in front of a painting, where we are dealing with a very complex semantic structure, as an artistic sign and not a simple sign of communication.

2. Theoretical framework

Image hermeneutics in postmodernity

2.1. Classical hermeneutics and its foundations

In the classical sense, hermeneutics encompasses the art and science of interpreting texts, established in the 19th–20th centuries by authors such as Dilthey, Hans-Georg Gadamer, and Paul Ricoeur. The main hermeneutic rules emerged from rhetoric, the art of speaking beautifully, built on the idea that the thought we seek to communicate must be presented efficiently within discourse. Here we consider the hermeneutic rule of the whole and the parts, according to which the parts of a writing can be understood only in the context of the whole that a discourse sums up and of its general intention.

H.-G. Gadamer (2005) insists on a pragmatic conception according to which truth is reduced to the utility it can have for me: it is not the work that adapts to my perspective, but, on the contrary, my perspective is the one that must expand, transforming itself in the proximity of the work. By following this reasoning, we notice that the work of art has its own truth, and to penetrate its meaning we must allow ourselves to be drawn into its play, a play in which we are enlivened by the image that stimulates our access to a higher stage.

By applying hermeneutics to the image, the work is transformed from a passive object into an active interlocutor, through which the subject is encouraged to formulate questions and to reconfigure their horizon of understanding.

2.2. Image hermeneutics

P. Ricoeur (1995) proposes two clear forms of interpretation that at first seem incompatible. The first derives from a *hermeneutics of trust*, which takes on a sense opposed to mere comprehension and guides consciousness by giving it a direction that belongs to a hermeneutics of exploration. The French hermeneutician P. Ricoeur (1995, p. 108) draws our attention to an essential trait related to the problem of discourse in a work of art, which could be connected to the definition of hermeneutics itself: “As reader, I find myself only by losing myself. Reading introduces me into the imaginative variations of the ego. The

metamorphosis of the world, according to play, is also the playful metamorphosis of the ego.” We observe in this way how the work of art contains organizational and structural features that make possible the extension to discourse of structural methods previously applied successfully to entities of language. It follows that a work of art must surpass its own psychosociological conditions of production and open itself to an infinite typology of readings that can occur in different sociocultural contexts and other spatio-temporal determinations.

C. G. Jung (2012, pp. 86–87) reminds us that works are rooted in a collective unconscious, and that “the creative process consists in the unconscious activity of an archetypal image. The artist who creates such works enriches the spirit of their time and compensates for the one-sidedness of the present.”

Through the art they practice, each artist tends in a certain way to become master of the universe, borrowing its warmth, its expressions, and its searches, which they later present to us, more or less intact, emptied of its own substance and replaced with that of the creator. In a similar vein, the painter Cézanne underlines the foundation of construction in a painting: to paint a landscape properly, one must first deepen the understanding of its geological layers. The image can offer meanings broader than sensation or perception, but to achieve this we must differentiate the image from the object. Here reflection comes into play, helping us distinguish image from object so that we do not risk taking it for another reality: through the image, the object reveals more of its profiles. The image can be a source of truth but also a source of error, and the “judgment” we make about these images can contribute to enriching knowledge of things, as J.-P. Sartre (1986) noted.

Image hermeneutics offers several principles that can serve as guiding lines:

- **the image as a visual text**, in which it can be “read,” interpreted, and analyzed using a method of stratified meanings;
- **contextualization**, in which meaning is influenced by cultural, historical, symbolic, and personal context;
- **interpretive dialogue**, where the image provokes questions and the interpreter brings their own cultural background;
- **multiplicity of meanings**, by which an image does not have a single meaning but a plurality of potential meanings;
- **aesthetic experience**, which brings the privilege of understanding the image by including both the emotional and the contemplative dimension.

In this order of ideas, image hermeneutics goes far beyond the framework of a simple formal analysis and directs us toward broad anthropological, cultural, theological, and existential meanings.

2.3. The postmodern dimension of visual interpretation

Postmodernism brings great openness toward diverse, contextualized, and reflective interpretations of the image. Pedagogy thus has the obligation to develop a theory required by an education whose role is to form the human being throughout the whole dimension of their life and in accordance with the needs of the next century. From here we deduce the necessity of adapting education to the demands of life by opening traditional (formal) education to various educational influences outside this context and, at the same time, transferring the spirit of this education into other educational areas.

Today, young people are not limited to being only receivers of information and consumers of products (spiritual, material, cultural, etc.), but also active participants in the creation of the common work typical of the nation to which they belong. Through participation, young people integrate into society, become active subjects of social action, a resource for moral and spiritual

progress, and the value predispositions and essential options of the young generation can be glimpsed in affective behaviors across different segments of their work and life. The active involvement of the subjects of education in their own formation must be perceived not only as an internalization of norms and requirements, but rather as an affective and voluntary engagement, reflected in the desire for development and self-perfection through active contact with socially desirable models of action.

The presence of postmodern didactics can be recognized as reflected in:

- dialogue and negotiation of meanings;
- interdisciplinarity (philosophy, history, aesthetics, theology, art history);
- emphasis on personal interpretation;
- integration of digital technologies;
- critical and reflective approaches.

3. Image hermeneutics in theological education

3.1. The image as a theological instrument

The image, according to theological tradition, has a privileged status because it conveys symbols, spiritual truths, cultural paradigms, and anthropological values. Through sacred art, iconography, and biblical or allegorical representations, students are offered indispensable means by which they can understand contextualized theology.

In this sense, I. Petrovici (1994, p. 212) states: “After Kant, religion is not in essence a manifestation different from morality; it has no separate essential foundations; its content is identical with that of morality.” We thus deduce that morality is what helps the human being overcome evil, selfish impulses and align with an adequate behavior in the direction of the categorical imperative of duty.

For the French philosopher-pedagogue René Hubert, religion occupies a plane superior to aesthetic feeling or the beautiful, which is nothing other than an

affective synthesis focused on a particular object, similar to erotic feeling. To reach fullness, the human being needs to rise to a more prodigious synthesis and to the representation of a relationship capable of uniting them not only to a single particular object of existence, but to the totality of existence.

What is the importance of religion in the educational context?

We answer by specifying that without religious instruction, young people would not be able to understand the abyssal layers full of meaning in painting, sculpture, architecture, and literature from different historical intervals. Religious education also holds substantial weight from a philosophical and moral point of view, because through its history, Christianity offers admirable examples of morality and philosophy regarding individual and collective life.

3.2. The role of hermeneutics in the formation of theological high school students

Through an image hermeneutics in a theological plan we understand the way in which human creation intertwines harmoniously by uniting human will with divine will, in the synergy of the two works: the divine and the human. From this perspective, the artistic language encountered in Christian iconography is determined by a norm created by Byzantine ingenuity, reflected in the iconographic canon. This norm shows us the form acquired by the creative relationship between God and the human being.

3.3. The connection between image, culture, and spirituality

Raphael's fresco, *The School of Athens*, in this sense, sums up a center of encounter between:

- Greek and Christian philosophy;
- reason and idealism;
- the learning community and the spiritual community.

This work represents the struggle between philosophy and religion over the knowledge of God, which is possible only through creation, and this, in turn, can only be indirect. The goal of education becomes much easier to achieve when students show favorable dispositions toward it. A small child anthropomorphizes everything easily: God, saints, angels; and in the period that follows, they reach a realistic, critical, and logical thinking, ultimately reaching the idea of rationally solving the question of religion. When adolescence follows, students lose some of the depth of metaphysical-religious concerns and turn with interest toward historical-social theories and ideas, in which they foresee meaning for an improvement of human societies. It follows that philosophy and theology find in artistic education not only a path of dissemination and theoretical elaboration, but also a way of being put into practice in perfect agreement with the requirements of various sectors of personal and social life.

4. Case study:

Hermeneutics of Raphael Sanzio's The School of Athens

4.1. Context of the work

This artwork comes to light at the initiative of Pope Julius II, who summons the painter Raphael Sanzio (1483–1520) to Rome to decorate the rooms of the pontifical apartment (called “stanze”). In one of these, one of his most prestigious creations takes shape: The School of Athens (1511). Within this monumental composition, Raphael brings to the fore a large number of ancient philosophers represented in different stances. The theme of this fresco addresses a delicate subject by capturing the harmony between Platonic and Aristotelian philosophy by the Renaissance artist. The key figures of the painting are Plato and Aristotle, who are equally the symbols of the two fundamental directions: idealism and realism; and around them are other philosophers such as Pythagoras,

Parmenides, Diogenes, Euclid, Zoroaster, Ptolemy, together with Raphael's self-portrait and that of his master Perugino.

4.2. Hermeneutic structure of the analysis

Through the hermeneutic analysis of the artwork applied in class with the students over three consecutive hours, we approached the following stages of investigation:

- the descriptive level, identifying the characters, composition, and architecture;
- the symbolic level, interpreting gestures, spatial relationships, and philosophical symbols;
- the theological level, connecting the message of the work to Christian values and to the idea of a community of knowledge;
- the reflective-personal level, through which the student notes what they understand, what challenges them, and the connections perceived as similar to their own experience;
- the socio-cultural level, in which students identify the relevance of the work in the current context of our society.

4.3. Hermeneutic meanings of the composition

4.3.1. The dialogue between Plato and Aristotle

In this section we note:

a. The existential function of the image.

We take note of the support of the painting, in this case the walls of pontifical apartments. Then, from the standpoint of representation, a scene with religious connotations is immortalized, namely the reconciliation of science with religion, where Plato is in fact Leonardo da Vinci, who had come to the Vatican in that period. In one hand he holds the book *Timaeus*, and with the other he points toward the sky the world of perfect ideas, where he believed the seat of

knowledge was. He represents by definition idealist philosophy, in contrast with Aristotle, who holds in his left hand the *Nicomachean Ethics*, and with his right points toward the earth, emphasizing the role of observation in the study of the world around us as the source of understanding. He is the representative of practical philosophy, and through his gesture he seems to affirm that the sciences have as their object of study morality and the application of experience. Through his extraordinary perspicacity and vast knowledge, he comes to be considered the father of experimental philosophy. Even the gesturality of the two philosophers can be interpreted as antagonistic: the idealism of the first overlaps the materialism affirmed by the other. From another angle, we notice the colors of Aristotle's garments, blue and brown, as a sign of water and earth (to emphasize the idea of a material philosophy), while in Plato's case the garments are blue and red, denoting air and fire. In the fresco there is also the group of the Peripatetics, represented by philosophers who followed Aristotle's philosophy; in the modern sense, the term "peripatetic" corresponds to an intellect that likes to discuss while walking. Next to this group appears the group of the Stoics with Zeno (334–262 BC), the founder of the doctrine according to which destiny rules the world, the universal law, fate, the strictest chain of cause and effect, together with Cleanthes and Chrysippus, the other leaders of the Stoic school. We also identify the group of the Hedonists, with the philosopher Epicurus (341–271 BC), depicted climbing the stairs as the founder of the Epicurean school. Epicurus's hedonism is not strictly limited to an apology of pleasure through lack of measure, but rather promotes a just regulation of pleasures, manifested in the philosopher's own contemplative, temperate, and virtuous life.

We then turn our attention to the group of Skeptics, where Raphael paints Pyrrho of Elis (360–270 BC), their representative, with a doctrine according to which we cannot hold certain knowledge about how things really are. Near him

could be Arcesilaus of Pitane (318–244 BC) or Plotinus (204–270 AD), a Neoplatonic philosopher, though his placement among Aristotle’s disciples is doubtful. Among philosophers and scholars, the Renaissance artist also chose to insert artists, which becomes a link between groups; toward the edge of the group of philosophers, Raphael places himself, accompanied by his master Perugino, as “listeners” to scholars and philosophers.

Following the convention of double identity, we might specify that Raphael embodies the Greek painter Apelles, given the nickname Vasari gave the master: “the new Apelles.” After careful analysis we identify the group of Euclid the geometer and his students, where the viewer’s contemplative spirit is carried toward the positive sciences. Euclid (325–265 BC) is none other than Donato Bramante, architect of St. Peter’s Basilica in Rome and a future mentor of the artist.

In the center of the assembly appears Diogenes of Sinope (412–322 BC), called “the Cynic,” reclining carelessly in sky-blue clothing, semi-nude, holding a tablet on which he meditates deeply, ignoring the celebrated gathering around him. The philosopher considered himself a “citizen of the world,” and when he remained without a house, he improvised a dwelling in a barrel; he wore the same cloak in winter and summer, begged for food, and despised townspeople for how they lived. The life he chose resembled that of a dog (*kynos* in Greek), and his doctrine received, in the 4th century BC, the name “cynicism.” The respect Diogenes earned extends to this day, when many philosophers see in him an absolute model of sincerity and, above all, a perfect symbiosis between idea and life. Our inquiry reaches the group on the right of the fresco, where Heraclitus of Ephesus is painted, who lived five hundred years before Christ. He belongs to the Ionian school, and Raphael, through this depiction, wished to pay homage to Michelangelo by giving him garments similar to the philosopher’s. His figure is

somewhat absent, as he is captured in meditation on the correlation between matter and spirit. Raphael chose to depict him turned with his back to the temple of knowledge and stretched on the steps, symbolizing that a person cannot “rise” toward the temple of wisdom before freeing intelligence from material hindrance.

b. Aesthetic function of the image

We identify this function in the way the composition was conceived, through an ingenious placement of characters in which the entire ensemble breathes an impeccable natural balance and harmony. From the standpoint of technique, this is a two-dimensional image that outlines the projection of the third dimension through shadows and linear perspective. Another level of analysis concerns reproduction: it is an artificial image, produced by the human hand in a voluntary act. The painting is a “fresco,” and thus we deal with a unique, original exemplar. The composition, though it appears simple, contains the geometric structure of the golden section and the simultaneity of monocular and binocular perspective (frontal, rising, and plunging). According to Renaissance philosophy, the human becomes an image-symbol and is placed at the center of attention by the artist through a personal interpretation of the Greek ideal of proportions formulated in Polykleitos’s Canon. Through Raphael’s genius, he combines the ethical and aesthetic values of Greek classicism with those of Christian morality and Renaissance Humanism (fashionable in the Platonic Academy of Florence), laying the foundations of a system of reference for the classical conception of harmony, valid for centuries in European art.

c. Cognitive function of the image

What did the artist seek to highlight through this image, and what is its message?

Through this work, Raphael values his conception of expressing the spiritual self and communicating ethical values through the artistic universe, as

well as the invitation to meditate on the fundamental role played, within the image, by the moral sense in close harmony with the sense of the sacred. In this large-scale fresco we observe scientific rigor focused on mathematics, geometric perspective and chromatic perspective, on the science of color harmony coupled with personal experience, procedures, and techniques of preparing pigments.

d. Hermeneutic function of the image

The School of Athens denotes a hidden meaning, of which we identify only an infinitesimal part at first contact. As good interpreters of Raphael's fresco, we must combine the information gathered through the other functions: aesthetic, cognitive, existential, then give them value in a particular knowledge through which we reach the quintessence of the artwork and its immense spiritual richness. J. J. Wunenburger (1973, p. 84) maintains that a "symbolic image can be approached only in the form of a visible, literal, immediate representation and is thus reduced to its surface."

Why does hermeneutics help us so much in understanding an image?

We answer by noting that because it calls upon the totality of human experience, in the sense of recognizing in the image the rational expressions of humanity it is natural that we cannot reach an abyssal interpretation if we set aside the hermeneutic process of interpretation. Through the hermeneutics of the artistic image, a multitude of aspects are revealed regarding content, context, pretext, and the artist's intentionality encoded in the subtext.

5. Research methodology

Applied to 9th grade, theological high school, Cultural Heritage section

5.1. Postmodern didactic approach

a. Principles

This research was carried out as a qualitative educational case study. The goal was to investigate the process of constructing meaning within a visual interpretation activity. On this occasion, we wish to underline the increasingly important role of artificial intelligence in the modern world. The machine is increasingly capable of guiding itself. G. Berger (1973) draws attention to the need for as many inventors as possible, whether for fundamental research, for transforming scientific truths into technical rules, or for social or administrative creation. The personalities education needs must possess extensive knowledge, but also a fertile imagination. Next, we formulate principles we must consider in the postmodern didactics of the educational process.

- **Interactivity and dialogue**

Through dialogue, the student does not receive meaning “ready-made,” but reaches the stage where they can build it through interpretation. They must be accustomed to the idea of a tomorrow that does not repeat yesterday, a tomorrow that allows to flourish what today exists only virtually. In this way, students become aware of the importance of deeply analyzing the present in which we live, in order to be prepared to extract from it the fundamental trends that orient us in one direction or another.

- **Personal reflection through reflective questionnaires**

The relationship that arises between students and the artwork cultivates and develops an intellectual work style adequate to each student, through forming and developing various abilities specific to intellectual activity (the ability to interpret, analyze material, synthesize, etc.), as noted by M. Ionescu and V. Chiş (2009). The image thus becomes a pretext that favors introspection.

- **Interdisciplinarity**

Here we witness teachers promoting students’ awareness of the importance of the symbiosis between particular theories of art (visual, musical,

literary) and contemporary methodologies (psychoanalytic, semiotic, sociological), which benefit both the receiver concerned with individualization and the aesthetician seeking generalization. Postmodern didactic lessons combine notions from philosophy with essential aspects from fields such as aesthetics, psychology, art history, anthropology, digital technologies, etc., bringing an innovative vision to contemporary education.

- **Integrating digital technologies**

Teaching visual grammar to students in vocational theological high schools, in the Cultural Heritage section, cannot be limited only to a simplified formal analysis; rather, it values the development of critical and reflective thinking toward visual messages, past and contemporary. With new and high-performance digital tools inserted into didactic pathways, we observe a total change in finalities, in how content is approached, and in how student effort is evaluated.

Educational platforms such as Padlet, Miro, and Canva provide not only asynchronous interaction among students, but also co-creation of visual content in a collaborative sequence that allows contextualized and in-depth learning.

5.2. Targeted learning objectives in this hermeneutic pathway

At the end of such an approach, students are able to achieve:

- an interpretive analysis of Raphael's fresco *The School of Athens*;
- identification of visual symbols and theological meanings in works of sacred art;
- connections between philosophy, theology, art history, and psychology of art;
- personal interpretation grounded in extensive argumentation;
- optimal use of digital tools in image analysis and 3D visualization.

Designing a hermeneutic lesson

Stage 1. Introductory notions (10 minutes)

In this sequence, the teacher presents the chosen work to students without giving additional explanations, while students use interpretation journals to take essential notes about what intrigues and moves them.

Stage 2. Exploring the image (20 minutes)

Divided into groups of four, students analyze the semantic structures of the painting, the arrangement of characters, and the dialogue established by the artist among them, using digital tools.

Stage 3. Hermeneutic interpretation (20 minutes)

The teacher facilitates dialogue about possible meanings of the scene, insisting on distinguishing the existential, aesthetic, cognitive, and hermeneutic functions of Raphael's fresco. Students observe the relationships among the characters and the main message *The School of Athens* conveys to the viewer.

Stage 4. Connecting the fresco with theology (20 minutes)

The teacher guides students in identifying the relationship between the religious value of an artwork and the moral value transmitted by it. In this way, they conduct a deep analysis of Christianity, which becomes the source of a new hermeneutics of the image, marked entirely by a strong ontological valence.

Stage 5. Personal reflection on the work (20 minutes)

Under the teacher's guidance, students write a short essay titled: "What meanings does the fresco *The School of Athens* inspire in me in my search for value and truth?".

Stage 6. Formative assessment

In this sequence, the teacher uses a hermeneutic rubric, establishing criteria regarding:

- accuracy of observations;
- depth of interpretation;

- capacity for argumentation;
- relevance of hermeneutic connections;
- originality of hermeneutic meanings.

6. Results of implementing the case study

By applying this hermeneutic didactic approach with 9th-grade students, the following aspects were observed:

- improvement of students' ability to formulate critical questions;
- increased student motivation to engage in interpreting Raphael's artwork;
- development of students' aesthetic, cultural, and philosophical sensitivity;
- deepening the connections between theology and visual culture;
- considerable growth of argumentation and personal reflection skills;
- gaining students' intellectual autonomy and confidence in expressing opinions.

6.1. Tables and graphs of results

Table 1. Results of the reflective questionnaire administered to students (N = 25)

Item	Affirmative response %	Interpretation
I understood the artwork more deeply	83%	Most students succeeded in interpreting the image beyond the descriptive level
I changed my perspective on art	89%	Students experienced a transformation of perception and meaning
The activity was more interesting than a traditional lesson	94%	The reflective method stimulated active engagement and curiosity
I felt I could personally contribute to the meaning of the work	78%	Interpretive participation was internalized

The table indicates the positive impact of the hermeneutic method on reflective learning and aesthetic motivation. The results can be summarized as follows: almost all students (94%) appreciated the method as more interesting, 89% reported a change of perspective, and 83% reported a deeper understanding of the work. The values indicate a significant internalization of the aesthetic and cognitive experience.

Table 2. Emerging themes from reflective journals

Hermeneutic axis	Frequency in journals %	Thematic description
Epistemological	72%	The image as a form of thinking and knowing
Aesthetic	61%	Beauty as a mode of understanding, not only contemplation
Identity-related	56%	Reflection on the self and one's own visual culture

Analysis of reflective journals highlights a process of self-reflective learning: students managed to connect the image to their own cultural experiences and to identify dimensions of the self through the artwork.

6.2. Visual graphs of results

Figure 1. Distribution of positive responses to the questionnaire

Figure 2. Emerging themes from reflective journals

The graphs clearly illustrate the positive impact of the hermeneutic approach on reflective learning and on developing critical thinking. A clear majority of affirmative responses is observed, as well as a balanced distribution of interpretive dimensions in students' journals.

7. Conclusions and research results

Image hermeneutics proves to be an innovative method in supporting education, while the educational process also faces challenges, including:

- students' difficulty in moving beyond the descriptive level toward an aesthetic-philosophical interpretation of an artwork;
- allocating the time necessary for deepened discussions;
- the real need for iconographic resources of high universal value.

In agreement with the above, M. Miclu (2008, p. 72) states: "Partners maintain a common ground; their notes interpenetrate and regulate each other." We deduce, therefore, that among students participating in the hermeneutic act and interacting with each other, a perceptual type of interdependence is created. From our observation we retain the aspect that perception ultimately intersects all other psychosocial analysis planes of competition (roles, communication, motivation, cognition), but especially inclines toward the attitudinal plane. As a result of applying this competitive process, we note the following typical aspects in the perceptual register:

- participants' sensitivity to perceiving similarities tends to decrease, while sensitivity to perceiving differences increases considerably;
- attention intensifies toward personal interests, to the detriment of others' interests;
- at the beginning of interactions, errors due to social perception tend to play a basic role in choosing behavioral strategies, and toward the end they tend to amplify and consolidate. As a concluding trait, we infer that image hermeneutics represents a solid foundation for postmodern didactics, with applicability in vocational theological high schools. The case study applied to *The School of Athens* brings to the surface the capacity of this method to generate meaning, dialogue, and deep reflection, since students transform into active participants in visual and spiritual knowledge, and the educational process reflects a cultural and existential dimension of great significance for the epistemological act. In

this context, image hermeneutics provides a new way of reconnecting visual (and artistic) education to the profound meaning of the cultural act, implicitly leading to the development of autonomy of thought, moral value judgment, aesthetic sensitivity, and not least, the digital skills acquired throughout this approach.

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